

MILITARY COOPERATION BETWEEN TURKEY AND KAZAKHSTAN**Soltanzade A.N.***Graduate student of the department of History
Baku State University, Azerbaijan***ВОЕННОЕ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВО МЕЖДУ ТУРЦИЕЙ И КАЗАХСТАНОМ****Солтанзаде А.Н.***Аспирант кафедры истории,
Бакинский государственный университет, Азербайджан***Abstract**

Kazakhstan has a very large territory due to its geography. Its land is 5 times that of Turkey. For this reason, after gaining independence, Kazakhstan began to build a security belt along its borders. However, the military and political relations between Turkey and Kazakhstan remained weak compared to Kazakhstan's relations with Russia and China. Despite this, the military and technical support of the Turkish government has been an important contribution to the development of the Armed Forces of Kazakhstan. From 1991 to 2001, 6 agreements were signed in the military field.

Аннотация

Казахстан имеет очень большую территорию в силу своего географического положения. Ее площадь в 5 раз больше, чем у Турции. Отношения между Турцией и Казахстаном в военно-политической сфере были слабыми по сравнению с отношениями Казахстана с Россией и Китаем. Несмотря на это, военно-техническая поддержка правительства Турции стала важным вкладом в развитие Вооруженных Сил Казахстана. С 1991 по 2001 год было подписано 6 соглашений в военной сфере.

Keywords: Turkey, Kazakhstan, military, agreement, armed forces**Ключевые слова:** Турция, Казахстан, военные, соглашение, вооруженные силы

Kazakhstan has a very large territory due to its geography. Its land is 5 times that of Turkey. For this reason, after gaining independence, Kazakhstan began to build a security belt along its borders. One of the first steps he took to protect his security was relations with Russia. On April 26, 1996, under the leadership of China, the Russian Federation, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Kazakhstan gathered in Shanghai and formed the Shanghai Five for mutual trust in military fields on the borders. According to the agreement, the parties should not maneuver against each other, and if there is a maneuver against one of them, and if there is a military action within 100 km of their borders, it is necessary to inform each other of this situation. At the same time, they decided to fight against drug and arms smuggling and terrorism.

However, the military and political relations between Turkey and Kazakhstan remained weak compared to Kazakhstan's relations with Russia and China. Despite this, the military and technical support of the Turkish government has been an important contribution to the development of the Armed Forces of Kazakhstan. From 1991 to 2001, 6 agreements were signed in the military field.

Since 2003, Kazakh officers began to study medicine at the Gulhane Military Medical Academy. Starting from 2004, courses in the Turkish language were created in the department of foreign languages at the Military Institute of the Ministry of Defense of Kazakhstan. Turkish special forces trained a Kazakh battalion under the command of Kazakh special forces. As a re-

sult of this program, more than 400 Kazakh officers acquired new skills thanks to the training they received. [1]

In 2005, Hilmi Ozkok, the former chief of general staff of Kazakhstan, met with Mukhtar Altynbayev, the defense president of Kazakhstan, in Astana and emphasized that the cooperation between the armed forces of the two countries, especially military training, is increasing day by day. He said that there are great opportunities for cooperation, especially in the field of defense, and that Turkey will continue to support the armed forces of Kazakhstan. Noting that Turkey is helping Kazakhstan with military ammunition, Mukhtar Altynbayev said that Kazakhstan will help Turkey with its resources in creating the Caspian fleet.

In 2005, Kazakhstan's armed forces received 24 land rovers (4 of them as ambulances), 28 backpack radios, 14 car radios, 50 hand-held radios, totaling more than 1 million dollars worth of military equipment. The military equipment was provided within the framework of the non-reciprocal military assistance agreement between Kazakhstan and Turkey. According to the protocol signed by Chief of Staff, Chief of Logistics Department Yurdar Olcan and Chief of Defense General Kajgaley Mukatov, Chief of Logistics Department of Kazakhstan, provision of military equipment, radio and devices for conducting night meetings of the armed forces of Kazakhstan in the fight against terrorism is envisaged. Speaking at the signing ceremony, General Olcan said that the military cooperation with Kazakhstan is mostly in the form of technical military assistance and educational assistance, including the creation

of anti-terrorism units and special security units. Turkey's unrequited technical military assistance to Kazakhstan exceeded 6 million dollars, it was reported. Kazakhstan is developing its military and technical relations with Turkey based on the principle of strategic partnership in the fight against international terrorism and religious fundamentalism in the world after September 11. [1]

Until 2006, 96 Kazakh officers completed their studies in Turkish military education fields, and 38 are continuing their studies. By 2011, more than 500 single Kazakhs had graduated from the Military Academy of the Republic of Turkey. Since 1993, the basis of bilateral relations has been providing military education to Kazakh youth.

Until 2010, agreements were signed in 11 military fields. The most important agreements made in the military field: the law on the approval of the military education agreement between the government of Kazakhstan and the government of Turkey, the agreement on educational, technical, scientific cooperation between Kazakhstan and Turkey in the military field, the agreement on the approval of the security cooperation protocol signed between the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Kazakhstan and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Turkey. These agreements further increased the cooperation between the two countries. [1]

An agreement was signed between Turkey and Kazakhstan on the possibilities of military cooperation for 2021.

The agreement prepared for 2021 was signed in Ankara and the directions of military cooperation between Kazakhstan and Turkey were determined. Before signing the contract, negotiations were held between the defense ministries of the two countries. During the negotiations, the Kazakh side was led by the head of the International Cooperation Department of the Ministry of Defense, Colonel Oljas Khusainov. [2]

The signed cooperation agreement includes a total of 17 activities, such as regional security issues, training of military units for special tasks, conducting joint exercises, exchanging tactics and experience on reconnaissance and attack UAVs. During the meetings, cooperation in the field of military education and science, as well as a plan for training military personnel in the 2022-2023 academic year, were agreed upon.

According to the news published in the Official Gazette of March 20, 2021, it was decided to approve the "Military Cooperation Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Turkey and the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan" signed in Ankara on September 13, 2018 by the President.

Approval of the "Agreement on military cooperation between the Government of the Republic of Turkey and the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan" with additional Notes in accordance with articles 2 and 3 of the additional Presidential Decree No. 9 signed in Ankara on September 13, 2018 and approved by Law No. 7271 it was decided to do. [2]

Forms of cooperation mentioned in the news include meetings and visits of high-ranking military officials, as well as activities such as the exchange of experience and information between experts from both

sides in various fields of activity. Organization of education, training or courses at military units, headquarters and institutions with paid, free or discounted fees; Other issues under the heading of forms of cooperation include contacts, joint negotiations, consultations and meetings between similar military institutions, participation in courses, symposia and conferences.

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Other ingredients include:

- To participate in military exercises, including actual shooting exercises, to participate in these military exercises as an observer, to organize joint exercises,
- Exchange of information and educational materials,
- Provide mutual material and technical support and exchange of ammunition, materials and services in the form of a grant or in exchange for payment,
- Participation in training projects, on-the-job training and career development courses.

In November 2021, the Ministry of Defense of Kazakhstan shared images of joint exercises involving Kazakh and Turkish soldiers. The Ministry of Defense of Kazakhstan shared the image of the joint exercise with the title "Kazakhstan-Turkey military cooperation". This image was published on all social media accounts of the ministry. The sharing included images from various exercises such as "Anadolu-21" and "Winter" in which the soldiers of the two countries participated together. During the training, the moments of joint operations performed by Kazakh and Turkish soldiers in the fields in different conditions were reflected. [3]

On May 10, 2022, a cooperation protocol in the field of military intelligence was signed between the Government of the Republic of Turkey and the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan. [5]

President of Kazakhstan Kasim Comert Tokayev arrived in Ankara to meet with President Recep Tayyip Erdogan. On his first official visit to Turkey after taking office, Tokayev was welcomed by President Erdogan with an official ceremony.

The Protocol on Military Intelligence Cooperation between the Government of the Republic of Turkey and the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Protocol on Cooperation in the Fields of Military Archives, Military History, Military Museums and Military Publications was signed by the Minister of National Defense of Turkey Hulusi Akar and the Minister of Defense of Kazakhstan Ruslan Jaxylykov. [4]

In bilateral military relations, Turkey was a carefully watched, interested and influenced country. In addition to historical and cultural relations, it can be said that Turkey's geopolitical structure and the fact that it is at a point where world trade routes intersect have an effect. For Kazakhstan, the fact that Turkey is a NATO member and a candidate country in the EU is seen by the EU as an actor that will increase its influence and

responsibility in relations with the region. This increases the importance of military relations.

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